

The mechanism of the intramolecular hydrocarbyl metathesis within a planar triruthenium cluster – combining core flexibility with hydride mobility

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Dedicated to Prof. Dr. Manuel G. Basallote

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Abstract: The transition metal catalyzed formation and cleavage of C–C bonds is of utmost importance in synthetic chemistry. While most of the existing homogeneous catalysts are mononuclear, knowledge of the behavior of polynuclear species is much more limited. By using computational methods, here we shed light into the mechanistic details of the thermally induced isomerization of $\text{Cp}^*_3\text{Ru}_3(\mu\text{-H})_2(\mu_3\text{-}\eta^2\text{-pentyne})(\mu_3\text{-pentylidyne})$ (**2**) into $\text{Cp}^*_3\text{Ru}_3(\mu\text{-H})_2(\mu_3\text{-}\eta^2\text{-octyne})(\mu_3\text{-ethylidyne})$ (**3**), a process that involves the migration of a C_3 fragment between the hydrocarbyl ligands and across the plane formed by the three Ru centers. Our results show this to be a complex transformation that comprises of five individual rearrangements in an $A \rightarrow B \rightarrow A \rightarrow B \rightarrow A$ order. Each so-called *rearrangement A* consists of the CH migration from the $\mu_3\text{-}\eta^2\text{-alkyne}$ into the $\mu_3\text{-alkylidene}$ ligand in the other side of the Ru_3 plane. This process is facilitated by the cluster's ability to adopt open-core structures in which one Ru–Ru bond is broken and a new C–C bond is formed. On the contrary, *rearrangements B* do not involve the formation or cleavage of C–C bonds nor do they require the opening of the cluster core. Instead, they consist of the isomerization of the $\mu_3\text{-}\eta^2\text{-alkyne}$ and $\mu_3\text{-alkylidyne}$ ligands on each side of the triruthenium plane into $\mu_3\text{-alkylidyne}$ and $\mu_3\text{-}\eta^2\text{-alkyne}$, respectively. Such transformation implies the migration of three H atoms within the hydrocarbyl ligands, and in this case it is aided by the cluster's ability to behave as a H reservoir. All in all, this study highlights the plasticity of these Ru_3 clusters, whereby Ru–Ru, Ru–C, Ru–H, C–C, and C–H bonds are formed and broken with surprising ease.

Introduction

The role of catalysis in our world can hardly be overemphasized. In Nature, a sheer number of years of catalysts' development and improvement have resulted in complex enzymes able to facilitate crucial reactions for life's viability. On an analogous but smaller timescale, researchers have modestly started studying the peculiarities of catalytic processes and applied them to obtain added value compounds. Notably, the majority of these catalysts involve transition metals (TM) in some form, and a clear distinction between homogeneous and heterogeneous TM-catalysts has traditionally been made. Mononuclear TM species are normally stabilized by interacting with surrounding ligands (in

solution) or another material (in the solid state), this already allowing to tune the properties of the resulting structures.^[1] Addition of a second TM results in the formation of homo- or heterodinuclear species that typically feature metal-metal interactions.^[2] This new degree of complexity has dramatic effects on the behavior of the catalysts, which not only have been thoroughly analyzed in the last decades but also represent a currently very active area of research.^[3] Evidently, *a priori* one can continue adding TMs to form tri-, tetra-, pentanuclear species and so on, thus increasing the complexity of the systems and the variety of forms that they can adopt. Importantly, while the bulk form of TMs shows properties that are in some way scalable, those of polynuclear clusters typically consisting of a few to a few thousand TM atoms do not usually vary gradually with size and have been designated to belong to the so-called non-scalable regime.^[4]

For decades the peculiar behavior of polynuclear TM-clusters has fascinated chemists,^[5] who knew they could open the door to unusual and unexpected phenomena. These structures are however often sensitive to the employed experimental conditions, and processes such as cluster fragmentation or isomerization have been described. Focusing on the homogeneous phase, for instance the $\text{Ru}_3(\text{CO})_{12}$ cluster is known to form mononuclear species when mixed with phosphine ligands under catalytic conditions, thus behaving only as a precatalyst for a number of active mononuclear Ru complexes.^[6] A probably more challenging scenario arises when the cluster is fluxional, which can happen both *prior to* or *during* catalysis.^[7] Such fluxionality is in fact strongly connected to the often uncommon behavior of TM-clusters, which includes the cleavage and formation of unexpected C–C bonds. This is the case of the trinuclear titanium heptahydride complex $[(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_4\text{SiMe}_3)\text{Ti}]_3(\mu_3\text{-H})(\mu\text{-H})_6$, which was shown recently to cleave the inert C–C bond of benzene,^[8] the process being coupled to the cleavage of a Ti–Ti bond and the formation of new metal–ligand interactions. An even more peculiar behavior has been observed by Suzuki et al. while studying the reaction of the Ru_3 polyhydrido cluster (**1**) with 1-pentene and 1-pentyne (Scheme 1).^[9] The resulting $(\mu_3\text{-pentylidyne})(\mu_3\text{-}\eta^2\text{-pentyne})$ species **2** is stable at room temperature, however, its thermolysis generates the $(\mu_3\text{-}\eta^2\text{-octyne})(\mu_3\text{-ethylidyne})$ cluster **3** via the formal migration of a C_3 fragment across the triruthenium plane.

Scheme 1. Formation of **2** and its thermal rearrangement into **3**.

These two processes clearly show how difficult it is to generalize the behavior of TM-clusters and why their reactivity must often be studied in a case by case basis. In this sense, it is worth noting that the advances in experimental techniques able to obtain information under operando conditions,^[10] in combination with computational methods,^[11] are crucial to a better understanding of the behavior of these complex systems, as exemplified by the recent studies on the Ti₃-mediated activation of benzene previously highlighted.^[12]

This manuscript describes the results of a computational investigation of the interconversion of **2** into **3**, which corresponds to a formal C₃ migration occurring under thermal conditions (Scheme 1). Surprisingly, to our knowledge computational methods have so far never been applied to this peculiar process and the only available mechanistic information is based on NMR and X-ray data.^[9] Such experimental information is nonetheless quite informative, as by carefully playing with the reaction temperature, the researchers were able to observe a number of reaction intermediates, ultimately leading them to propose the multistep mechanism shown in Scheme 2. Thus, the overall reaction is believed to involve two different types of rearrangement, labelled here as *A* and *B*, which take place in an alternative manner. The so-called *rearrangement A* consists of the migration of a CH unit from a μ_3 -alkylidyne into a μ_3 - η^2 -alkyne ligand, and it has been

proposed to involve open-core intermediates.^[9] Once a *rearrangement A* has taken place, before the next similar rearrangement can proceed the hydrocarbonyl ligands within the resulting species have to undergo an additional isomerization for which no mechanistic proposal has even been formulated. In other words, species **A** in Scheme 2, featuring μ_3 -butylidyne and μ_3 - η^2 -hexyne ligands, must first be converted into μ_3 - η^2 -butyne and μ_3 -hexylidyne ligands, respectively. This rearrangement, denoted here as *B*, does not modify the number of C atoms within these hydrocarbonyl ligands but only involves H migrations. Moreover, based on the experimentally required reaction temperatures, it features free energy barriers slightly larger than those of *rearrangements A*.

By using the previous experimental information as a starting point, herein we employed computational DFT methods on the full system to shed light on: (1) the mechanistic details of the so-called *rearrangements A* and *B*; (2) how their barriers vary with the length of the alkyl ligand, which allows explaining why transformation from **2** to **3** occurs; (3) the reasons why **3** does not undergo an additional *rearrangement B*.

Results and Discussion

Mechanism of the so-called rearrangement A.

The isomerization of **2** into **A**, whereby the C–H moiety of the μ_3 - η^2 -pentyne ligand is transferred across the Ru₃ plane to generate a μ_3 - η^2 -hexyne ligand, has been used as a model for this rearrangement (See Scheme 2). The study was started by optimizing the structures of these species, which feature a Ru₃ core with relatively similar Ru–Ru bond distances (ca. 2.7–2.8 Å), with the μ_3 -alkylidyne and μ_3 - η^2 -alkyne ligands in opposite sides of the plane formed by those three metal centers. Notably, in the case of **2**, low temperature NMR experiments have shown that it exists as a mixture of two isomers in a 90:10 ratio that differ in the position of the μ -H ligands.^[9] Note that there are only two μ -H ligands but three possible bridging sites between the metal centers. In agreement with this data, a 70:30 ratio ($\Delta G=0.45$ kcal mol⁻¹) is computed in favor of the major isomer, whose structure is included in Figure 1 (see Figure S1 for the minor isomer). Interestingly, at the selected computational level **A** is found to be only 0.1 kcal mol⁻¹ less stable than **2**, and thus the process can be practically considered thermoneutral (see Scheme 3). This is again in agreement with NMR experiments showing the formation of roughly equimolar mixtures of these species after 1 h at 80 °C. Moreover, this reaction free energy shows that,

Scheme 2. Multistep mechanism proposed by Suzuki et al.^[9] for the isomerization of **2** into **3**. Cp* ligands are omitted for clarity.

evidently, an increase/decrease in one C unit in these hydrocarbonyl ligands only results in small free energy differences. Based on the behavior of analogous Ru₃ hydride clusters it has been proposed that this transformation may involve intermediates featuring open-cluster structures in which a Ru–Ru bond is broken and a C–C bond formed between the CH moiety of the terminal alkyne ligand and the μ₃-C center of the alkylidyne.^[9] Indeed, gradual shortening of the C5–C6 distance in **2** resulted in the formation of intermediate **I1** (see Figure 2a), in which the Ru2 and Ru3 centers are located 3.80 Å apart (cf. 2.76 Å in **2**) while a bond between C5 and C6 is now evident (d(C5–C6)= 1.49 Å, cf. 2.90 Å in **2**). The formation of **I1** takes place via **TS**_{2-I1} (see Figure 1), a transition state that shows already a significant elongation of the Ru2–Ru3 distance (3.39 Å), while the C5–C6 interaction is still almost inexistent (2.57 Å). The cleavage of such Ru–Ru bond without any clear additional stabilization is probably the origin of the relatively high free energy (36.6 kcal mol⁻¹) of this structure. Nevertheless, such value is in qualitative agreement with temperatures and times required for the process to take place.

Importantly, not only **I1** can revert into **2** via **TS**_{2-I1}, but also it can evolve into the **A** by means of **TS**_{I1-A} (37.7 kcal mol⁻¹, see Figure S2). These two transition states are in fact quite similar both energetically and structurally, with the exception that the C6–C7 bond is broken in **TS**_{I1-A}. Thus, the overall isomerization represented in Scheme 3 consists of the opening of the cluster core and formation of a C5–C6 bond in **I1**, followed by the closing of the cluster core and cleavage of the C6–C7 bond in **A**. The transition states for both steps show similar free energies of ca. 37 kcal mol⁻¹, with the intermediate **I1** appearing 7.3 kcal mol⁻¹ above **2**. Both transformations are reversible, and thus equilibration between **2** and **A** will take place when the system is given enough energy to overcome such barriers. Experimentally, no reaction intermediates were observed when monitoring the process via NMR spectroscopy, which is in accordance with the relative instability of **I1** against **2** and **A**. As the evolution of **I1** into **2** or **A** is faster than its formation, no large quantities of **I1** will be formed.

Notably, the two-step mechanism proposed for this *rearrangement A* in Scheme 3 share similarities with the generally accepted mechanism for alkyne metathesis at monometallic species,^[13] as **I1** resembles the metallacyclobutadiene generated by the hypothetical [2+2] cycloaddition between the Ru1≡C5 and C6=C7 moieties, with the conversion of **I1** into **A** corresponding to the subsequent retro-[2+2] cycloaddition step. The system here is nonetheless much more complex, as the three C atoms involved in the rearrangement are also interacting with the Ru2 and Ru3 centers. Indeed, as shown in Figure 2a, both C5 and C7 are bound to Ru2 and Ru3 with distances between 2.14 and 2.24 Å. Moreover, these C atoms are both linked to C6 and the rest of their alkyl chains (C4 and C8, respectively), thus leading to hypercoordinate C centers.^[14] A similar coordination environment can in fact be suggested for C6, although in this case there is no Ru1–C6 bond (2.80 Å) and instead the penta-coordination is completed via the C6–H3 bond. Five-coordinate C atoms have been described in a variety of structures,^[14] as for instance in the ruthenacyclobutane intermediates formed during the metathesis of olefins in the presence of Grubbs' catalysts.^[15] In this case, the three consecutive penta-coordinated C atoms are probably more reminiscent of carborane cages, where various

Scheme 3. Computed free energy profile (kcal mol⁻¹) for the isomerization of **2** into **A**. Cp* ligands are omitted for clarity.

Figure 1. Computed structures (Å, °) of **2** and **TS**_{2-I1}. Cp* rings and part of the alkyl ligands are omitted for clarity.

Figure 2. a) Computed structure of **I1** (Cp* rings and part of the alkyl ligands are omitted for clarity) together with selected bond distances (d, Å), Wiberg bond indices (WBI) and delocalization indices (DI); Contour line diagrams ∇²ρ(r) of **I1** at the C5–C6–C7 and Ru1–Ru2–Ru3 planes. Bond, ring and cage critical points are shown as blue, orange and green spheres, respectively. See the Supporting Information for QTAIM metrics.

consecutive hypercoordinate C centres can be bound to each other.^[16]

Wiberg bond indices (WBI) derived from natural bond orbital (NBO) calculations,^[17] as well as delocalization indices (DI) defined in the context of the quantum theory of atoms in molecules (QTAIM),^[18] have been employed to estimate the strength of the bonds that C5, C6 and C7 form, and to confirm the bonding picture previously described. Indeed, despite the expected differences in computed WBI and DI values, they both agree in the presence of hypercoordinate C atoms. In addition, Wiberg bond indices are able to discriminate C–C and C–H bonds (ca. 0.85–1.05) from C–Ru bonds (ca. 0.35–0.65). Focusing on the C6 center, further insight into its penta-coordinate character in **I1** can be obtained from a quantum theory of atoms in molecules (QTAIM)^[18] study (see Figure 2b), which shows bond critical points (BCPs) between this and C5, C7, H3, Ru2 and Ru3 centers. Note that the symmetry of this structure, containing two perpendicular cyclic units (i.e. {Ru1, C5, C6, C7} and {Ru1, H1, Ru2, C6, Ru3, H2}), leads to additional QTAIM features such as a shared ring critical point (rcp1) at the center of these perpendicular planes, and symmetrical ring (rcp2') and cage (ccp1 and ccp1') critical points at the cavities created within this open-core structure.

Mechanism of the so-called rearrangement B.

In the previous section it was shown that the $\mu_3\text{-}\eta^2$ -pentyne and μ_3 -pentyldiyne ligands in **2** can isomerize into μ_3 -butyldiyne and $\mu_3\text{-}\eta^2$ -hexyne, respectively, to form **A** by means of a rearrangement A. As shown in Scheme 2, besides reverting into **2**, **A** cannot undergo the next C–H moiety transfer across the Ru₃ plane that would result in ligands with three and seven C atoms. Instead, for this to be possible the μ_3 -butyldiyne and $\mu_3\text{-}\eta^2$ -hexyne ligands in **A** must first undergo a rearrangement B that will render $\mu_3\text{-}\eta^2$ -butyne and μ_3 -hexyldiyne, respectively. In this section the isomerization of **A** into **B** has been studied as a model for rearrangement B. Mechanistically, this transformation is much more complex than the previous one because it involves the cleavage of three C–H bonds and the formation of three new C–H bonds. Specifically, this process can be viewed as a complex migration of three H atoms within C5, C6, C7 and C8, as in **A** they are bound to C6 and C8 whereas in **B** they are bound to C5 and C7. In addition, based on the “location” of these H atoms, it is logical to think that two of those H migrations will take place within each hydrocarbonyl ligand, i.e., from C8 to C7 and from C6 to C5, with another one taking place across the Ru₃ plane, i.e. from C8 to C5. There are two obvious mechanistic questions that one can think of at this point: a) In which order do these H migrations take place? Assuming that each one represents an independent event, there are six alternative ways or ordering them (see below); b) What is the most likely mechanism for each H migration and what is the role of the Ru₃ cluster? As noted above, it is logical to assume each of them has its own mechanistic details. This is obvious if we take into account that, while two of those H migrations must take place within each hydrocarbonyl ligand, there is another one (from C8 into C5) whereby the H atom must cross the Ru₃ plane. In this sense, it is worth noting that the migration of bridging hydride ligands within this^[19] and other^[20] trinuclear complexes has been described, thus making likely their participation in the process. Nevertheless, to answer these questions the study was initiated by analyzing whether 1,2-H migrations within each hydrocarbonyl

Scheme 4. Computed free energy profiles (kcal mol⁻¹) for the possible initial rearrangements of cluster **A**. Cp* ligands are omitted for clarity. Note that a different perspective was used to draw **I3**.

ligand can take place without participation of μ -H ligands or the metal centers (see Scheme 4). Specifically, these included the rearrangement of the $\mu_3\text{-}\eta^2$ -hexyne ligand to form **I3** (i.e. formal H migration from C6 to C5), and that of the μ_3 -butyldiyne to generate **I5** (i.e. formal H migration from C8 to C7). As expected for an uncatalyzed 1,2-H migration within an hydrocarbonyl ligand, the direct **A**→**I3** rearrangement is computed to take place with a free energy barrier (**TS_{A-13}**, 69.3 kcal mol⁻¹) that clearly allows discarding this step as operative. In the case of the **A**→**I5** rearrangement, all attempts to obtain a transition state for such process were unsuccessful. Instead, they resulted in the optimization of another unlikely process that connects **A** with the Ru₃(μ -H)₃ containing species **I7** (21.7 kcal mol⁻¹). Given that these results are at odds with the experimental data, which suggests that the whole **A**→**B** transformation takes place with lower free energy barriers, we turned our attention into the possible participation of μ -H ligands in the formation of **I3** and **I5**. Expectedly, our computations showed that such mechanistic possibility allows obtaining both intermediates with significantly lower barriers. In this way, the H migrations can take place in a stepwise manner, with a (μ -H) ligand initially being transferred into the accepting C atom, followed by a H transfer from the

donating C atom into the Ru_3 plane to restore the $Ru_3(\mu-H)_2$ core. Thus, the transfer of a ($\mu-H$) ligand into the C5 atom of **A** generates the Ru_3H -containing intermediate **I2** (16.1 kcal mol⁻¹) via **TS**_{A-12} (15.8 kcal mol⁻¹). Subsequently, **I2** can undergo a second H migration from C6 into the Ru_3 plane via **TS**_{I2-13} (19.6 kcal mol⁻¹) that restores the Ru_3H_2 core and generates **I3**. Analogously, a ($\mu-H$) in **A** can also migrate into the C7 atom of the μ_3 -butylidyne ligand to generate **I4** (25.5 kcal mol⁻¹), which can later form **I5** via the cleavage of a C8-H bond (**TS**_{I4-15}, 35.5 kcal mol⁻¹). Evidently, the viability of such stepwise mechanisms is linked to the capability of the Ru_3 cluster to stabilize hydrocarbonyl ligands beyond μ_3 - η^2 -alkyne and μ_3 -alkylidyne by forming intermediates containing a $Ru_3(\mu-H)$ core such as **I2** and **I4**. In addition, these structures can serve as a link to more than two $Ru_3(\mu-H)_2$ containing species, as exemplified in Scheme 4 with the formation of **I6** from **I2**. In fact, the **A**→**I2**→**I6** transformation explains how a H atom could migrate from C8 to C5, i.e. from μ_3 -butylidyne to μ_3 - η^2 -hexyne across the Ru_3 plane. The isomerizations of **A** into **I3**, **I5** and **I6** in Scheme 4 thus correspond to the three individual H migrations that **A** can initially undergo. *A priori*, each of these intermediates can further evolve into **B** by undergoing two additional stepwise H migrations. For instance, **I3** can now suffer a H migration from C8 to C7 and another one from C8 to C5, in this order or the opposite, and this would result in the formation of **B**. Note that this leads to two alternative mechanisms that share intermediate **I3**. As noted above, the same is true for **I5** and **I6** and therefore a total of six alternative mechanisms are possible. Fortunately, from the data in Scheme 4 it is already possible to discard some of these pathways. Indeed, the formation of **I6** requires overcoming a free energy barrier of 62.5 kcal mol⁻¹ (**TS**_{I2-16}) that

allows rejecting any possible mechanism involving this species. In relation to **I5**, i.e. the product of the 1,2-H migration within the μ_3 -butylidyne ligand, the two alternative mechanisms that connect it with product **B** imply the formation of **I8** (see Scheme 5). Note that, for **I5** to reach **B** the H atoms at C6 and C8 must be transferred into C5, and therefore both mechanisms will share an intermediate (**I8**) in which one of the ($\mu-H$) ligands has been transferred to C5. Not only the transition state for the formation of **I8** is found to be energetically too demanding (**TS**_{I5-18}, 71.1 kcal mol⁻¹), but also **I8** itself is 52.3 kcal mol⁻¹ less stable than **A**, all this suggesting that any pathway involving its formation will not be productive. It is worth noting at this point that the relative instability of this structure is probably associated with the poor donating ability of the two hydrocarbonyl ligands, which present a distorted π -coordination to different Ru centers. This is evidenced by the appearance of complementary C-H...Ru contacts, which suggest that the electronic requirements of the metal centers are not fully covered.

Scheme 5. Computed free energy profile (kcal mol⁻¹) for the isomerization of **I5** into **I8**, with all energies quoted with respect to **A**. Cp* ligands are omitted for clarity.

Scheme 6. Computed free energy profiles (kcal mol⁻¹) for the isomerization of **I3** into **B**, with all energies quoted with respect to **A**. Cp* ligands are omitted for clarity.

Figure 3. Computed structures (Å) of **TS**_{111-I12a}, **I3**, **TS**₁₃₋₁₉ and **I9**. Cp* rings and part of the alkyl ligands are omitted for clarity.

The computations so far suggest that the conversion of **A** into **B** starts with the cluster-catalyzed 1,2-H migration within the μ_3 - η^2 -hexyne ligand that results in **I3**. From this species, the two possible mechanisms leading to **B** are included in Scheme 6. Thus, one possible scenario consists of the cluster-catalyzed 1,2-H migration within μ_3 -butylidyne ligand to generate intermediate **I11**. Based on the computed free energy of its rate-determining step (**TS**_{110-I11}, 35.3 kcal mol⁻¹), this process could indeed take place experimentally. However, the final stepwise H migration required for **I11** to reach **B**, i.e. the migration of a H atom from C8 to C5 across the Ru₃ plane, is found to be too energy-demanding, which suggests that this pathway is not operative. Specifically, the formation of **I12a** is not only very endergonic (45.0 kcal mol⁻¹), but it is also found to feature a prohibitive activation barrier (**TS**_{111-I12a}, 56.9 kcal mol⁻¹). Despite it does not affect the previous statement, it is worth noting that the conversion of **I11** into **B** is found to take place in three consecutive steps, i.e. differing from previous two-step H migrations in that here there is an additional step related to the cleavage of the agostic C5-H...Ru interaction found in intermediate **I12a**.

Alternatively, in our proposed mechanism **I3** does not evolve into **I11** but it is converted into **I9** (see Scheme 6 and Figure 3). In fact, **I9** represents a crucial species within this proposal because it features two μ_3 -alkylidyne ligands bound to the Cp*₃Ru₃H core.^[21] The whole transformation of **A** into **I9** can then be seen as the rearrangement of the μ_3 - η^2 -hexyne ligand into μ_3 -hexylidyne, with all the steps involved taking place in the same side of the Ru₃ plane. The subsequent transformation of **I9** into **B**, consisting of the isomerization of the μ_3 -butylidyne ligand into μ_3 - η^2 -butyne, will occur in the other side of the Ru₃ plane. Moreover, this can take place by means of the same steps that previously allowed generating **I9**, but in reverse order. As shown in Figure 4, the whole transformation of **A** into **B** can then be split in two halves: (a) the conversion of the μ_3 - η^2 -hexyne ligand into μ_3 -hexylidyne; (b) the conversion of the μ_3 -butylidyne ligand into μ_3 - η^2 -butyne. Note that the only difference between the two halves of the process is the number of C atoms of the hydrocarbyl ligands, which explains the relatively symmetric free energy profile and why the species formed after **I9** within this mechanistic proposal were labelled as **I3'** and **I2'**. **I9** thus represent a reaction intermediate from where either **A** or **B** can be obtained depending on the relative barriers and stabilities of the species involved. Based on the results in Figure 4, **A** and **B** almost feature the same relative stability, which explains why heating a sample of **A** results in the partial formation of **B**. Kinetically, the conversion of **I3** into **I9**, and that of **I9** into **I3'**, which overall results in the transfer of a H atom from C8 to C5, correspond to the most energy demanding steps of the process, as once **I3'** is formed, its rearrangement into **B** is much more facile. Note that the transition states **TS**₁₃₋₁₉ (37.6 kcal/mol) and **TS**_{19-I3'} (37.4 kcal/mol) are both structurally and energetically very similar. Specifically, **TS**₁₃₋₁₉ allows transferring the bridging H ligand initially located between Ru1 and Ru2 into the C5 center. Its structure, included in Figure 3, shows how the interaction between Ru2 and the H ligand is already broken at this point, at the same time that the new C5-H bond (1.52 Å) is partly formed. Moreover, this H migration is facilitated by the Ru1 center, which serves as a bridge between **I3** and **I9** by interacting with both C5 and the transferred H center. Note that such interactions vanish once the μ_3 -hexylidyne ligand is fully formed in **I9**.

Based on the free energy profile for the conversion of **A** into **B** in Figure 4, the overall activation barrier for this *rearrangement B* is only slightly higher than that for the previously computed *rearrangement A*. This is in qualitative agreement with the experiments showing that higher temperatures are required for each *rearrangement B* to take place, which considering the complexity of the whole transformation can be thought of as an indicative of the viability of the mechanistic proposal. An additional feature on its favor is given by the experimental non-observation of intermediates when the conversion of **A** into **B** is monitored by NMR spectroscopy, as all the proposed intermediates between **A** and **B** are less stable than these species. The formation of any intermediate will be slower than its disappearance, and therefore it will not be observed by NMR spectroscopy. Note that a similar scenario was found in the previous section when studying a *rearrangement A*, which explained the non-observation of **I1**. All in all, the computations herein suggest that the isomerization of **A** into **B** takes place via six consecutive H migration processes that not only involve the C5, C6, C7 and C8 atoms of the hydrocarbyl ligands, but also the (μ -H) ligands of the cluster. These steps can be thought of

Figure 4. Computed free energy profile (kcal mol^{-1}) for the isomerization of **A** into **B** (solid line, energies in bold, quoted relative to **A**). The analogous profile for the isomerization of **3** into **E** is also included (dashed line, energies in italics, quoted relative to **3**).

as three cluster-catalyzed two-step H migrations from: (a) C6 to C5; (b) C8 to C5; (c) C8 to C7. Of these, the first and third H migrations take place within each hydrocarbonyl ligand and side of the Ru_3 plane, whereas that from C8 to C5 takes place from one ligand to the other and across the Ru_3 plane. This latter process is found to be rate-determining, involving the formation of the transient Ru_3H bis-alkylidyne intermediate **19**.

Overall isomerization of **2** into **3**.

Based on the previous results it is logical to assume that the proposed mechanisms for the so-called *rearrangements A and B* will, *a priori*, apply regardless of the number of C atoms of each hydrocarbonyl ligand. At this point however one could wonder: a) why the series of rearrangements in Scheme 2 experimentally stop when **3** is reached?; b) could not **3** undergo an additional *rearrangement B* resulting in the formation of the $(\mu_3\text{-ethyne})(\mu_3\text{-octylidyne})$ species **E** shown in Scheme 7?

Our previous computations have shown that small changes in stability arise when the length of the hydrocarbonyl ligands varies, and for instance species **2** was computed to be only $0.1 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ more stable than **A**. To better understand this effect, the structure of all the species in Scheme 2 has been computed, and their relative free energy with respect to **2** included in Table 1. In agreement with the experiments, this shows that **3** represents the thermodynamic product ($-4.2 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$), therefore explaining why it is obtained when the necessary barriers are surmounted. Nevertheless, to further analyze the origin of these free energy values they have been decomposed in Table 1 in the three main terms of which they are composed (PBE0/BS2(SMD) electronic energy, thermal and entropic corrections required to obtain free energy values, and D3(BJ) correction for the dispersion effects), and their values also quoted relative to that of species **2**. Their analysis shows that the $\Delta(E \rightarrow G)_{\text{corr}}$ term plays a minor role in determining which isomer is thermodynamically more stable, at least for the conversion of **2** into **3**. On the contrary, it is the balance between electronic energy (ΔE) and dispersion corrections ($\Delta(\text{D3BJ})_{\text{corr}}$)

Scheme 7. Equilibrium between **3** and **E**.

Table 1. Computed relative free energies (ΔG) of **2**, **A**, **B**, **C**, **D**, **3** and **E**, and differences in their computed electronic energies (ΔE), $E \rightarrow G$ correction ($\Delta(E \rightarrow G)_{\text{corr}}$), and dispersion correction ($\Delta(\text{D3BJ})_{\text{corr}}$). All values are given in kcal/mol , quoted relative to **2**.

Species	ΔG	ΔE	$\Delta(E \rightarrow G)_{\text{corr}}$	$\Delta(\text{D3BJ})_{\text{corr}}$
2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
A	0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.3
B	0.0	0.0	-0.5	0.5
C	0.9	-0.3	0.0	1.2
D	-0.3	-2.8	0.4	2.1
3	-4.2	-7.2	-0.4	3.4
E	0.6	-3.1	-1.2	4.8

which seems to truly determine the relative stability of each structure. The dispersion correction term follows the expected trend as we go from **2** to **E**, as on average this series of isomerizations lead to structures where fewer C and H atoms are in the proximities of the Cp^*_3Ru_3 core, and therefore they become less stabilized by these forces. The behavior of the electronic energy term is slightly more complex. The data shows that the relative electronic energies of **2**, **A**, **B** and **C** are all within $0.3 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, which indicates that the donating properties of μ_3 -alkylidyne and μ_3 - η^2 -alkyne ligands with four to seven C atoms are probably comparable (see Scheme 2). This however changes when we reach structures featuring hydrocarbyl ligands with two to three C atoms, as in **D**, **3**, or **E**. In such cases stabilizations between $3\text{--}7 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ are found. It is useful at this point to compare pair of structures in which the “small” ligand differs in one C unit, such as **D** and **E**, or **C** and **3**. Notably, **D** and **E** almost feature the same relative electronic energies, which indicates that the donating properties of μ_3 - η^2 -propyne and μ_3 - η^2 -ethyne are not too different. Note that we are assuming that the additional C atom at the μ_3 -alkylidyne ligand will not modify its donating properties. The conclusion is completely different when we compare **C** and **3**, as moving from a μ_3 -propylidyne ligand in **C** to a μ_3 -ethylidyne ligand in **3** results in a crucial stabilization of ca. 7 kcal mol^{-1} . Thus, it seems that the stabilization associated with the formation of the μ_3 -ethylidyne ligand in **3** is significant enough to overcome the accompanying destabilization due to the decrease in dispersion forces, ultimately explaining why **3** represents the thermodynamic product of the system.

Interestingly, in their original paper^[9] Suzuki et al. suggested that the isomerization of **3** into **E** could be hampered by a too high activation barrier for the conversion of the μ_3 -ethylidyne ligand into μ_3 - η^2 -ethyne, thus kinetically stabilizing the observed product **3**. Although the computations in Table 1 indicate that thermodynamic reasons are ultimately responsible, the free energy profile for the isomerization of **3** into **E** has been computed in order to test their hypothesis and to which extent the change in the number of C atoms of the hydrocarbyl ligands affects the barriers of a *rearrangement B*. The corresponding results are included in Figure 4, which allows for a direct comparison with the analogous isomerization of **A** into **B**. It is worth reminding that these profiles can be viewed as two consecutive multistep processes, the first one consisting on the rearrangement of the μ_3 - η^2 -alkyne ligand into μ_3 -alkylidyne, thus generating a Ru_3H cluster with two μ_3 -alkylidyne ligands; and a second one in which the initial μ_3 -alkylidyne ligand evolves into μ_3 - η^2 -alkyne. Regarding the μ_3 - η^2 -alkyne into μ_3 -alkylidyne transformation (first half of the profile), it is found that differences only in the range of $0\text{--}1 \text{ kcal/mol}$ are obtained for the hexyne (**A**) and octyne (**3**) ligands. Moreover, given that these relative free energies are also similar to those computed for the μ_3 - η^2 -butyne into μ_3 -butylidyne transformation that connects **B** with **19** (second half of the profile, in reverse order), it can be concluded that the free energy profiles for such transformations on hydrocarbyl ligands with four, six, or eight C atoms are roughly identical. On the contrary, the differences are obvious in the second half of the profile in Figure 5, corresponding to the μ_3 -alkylidyne into μ_3 - η^2 -alkyne transformations of hydrocarbyl ligands with four and two C atoms. In fact, all the structures associated with the rearrangement of the μ_3 - η^2 -ethyne ligand are destabilized by ca. $4\text{--}5 \text{ kcal/mol}$, which not only explains the relative instability of **E**,

but it is also in agreement with Suzuki's hypothesis on the kinetically hampered nature of its formation.

Conclusions

In this study we successfully carried out an *in silico* mechanistic analysis of a peculiar example of cluster isomerization, from $\text{Cp}^*_3\text{Ru}_3(\mu\text{-H})_2(\mu_3\text{-}\eta^2\text{-pentyn})(\mu_3\text{-pentylidyne})$ (**2**) into $\text{Cp}^*_3\text{Ru}_3(\mu\text{-H})_2(\mu_3\text{-}\eta^2\text{-octyn})(\mu_3\text{-ethylidyne})$ (**3**), that involves the formation and cleavage of a number of Ru–Ru, Ru–C, Ru–H, C–C and C–H bonds. The results, in full agreement with the experimental data, indicate that this complex transformation consists of a series of alternating *rearrangements A* and *B*.

Rearrangements A imply a CH migration from the μ_3 - η^2 -alkyne into the μ_3 -alkylidyne ligand on the other side of the Ru_3 plane. These processes are facilitated by the cluster's ability to adopt open-core structures in which one Ru–Ru bond is broken. *Rearrangements B* consists of the isomerization of the μ_3 - η^2 -alkyne and μ_3 -alkylidyne ligands on each side of the Ru_3 plane into μ_3 -alkylidyne and μ_3 -alkyne, respectively. These processes are mechanistically much more complex than *rearrangements A*, although they do not involve the formation or cleavage of Ru–Ru or C–C bonds but only of C–H and Ru–H bonds. *Rearrangements B* do not require the opening of the cluster core skeleton and, instead, they are facilitated by its capability to behave as a H reservoir, catalyzing each of the three necessary H migrations by forming intermediate Ru_3H -containing species. Moreover, the computations show that the order in which these H migrations is very specific, with the overall rate-determining step being the formation of a bis-alkylidyne intermediate.

Thermodynamically, the isomerization of **2** into **3** is driven by the larger stability of the latter species, and further analysis of these structures suggests that it originates from the better donating properties of the μ_3 -ethylidyne ligand with respect to longer μ_3 -alkylidyne analogues.

Computational details

Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations were run with Gaussian16 software,^[22] employing the PBE0 functional.^[23] This density functional was selected based on its good performance on Ru complexes, both in terms of structural parameters^[24] and reaction energies.^[25] Additional tests have been included in the Supporting Information. Gas-phase geometry optimizations were carried out without symmetry constraints in the (closed shell) singlet potential energy surface and employed the so-called “ultrafine” integration grid. These calculations used the SDD pseudopotentials and associated basis sets to describe the Ru atoms,^[26] whereas all other atoms were described using the Pople style 6-31G(d,p) basis set.^[27] This basis set combination is designated as BS1. All stationary points were characterized at the PBE0/BS1 level of theory as minima or transition structures via analytical frequency calculations. This also allowed deriving the thermal and entropic corrections, $(E \rightarrow G)_{\text{corr}}$, required to obtain free energies at 298.15 K and 1 M. The connection between transition states, reactants and products was verified by performing IRC calculations using the Gonzalez and Schlegel algorithm^[28] implemented in Gaussian16.

Electronic energies were refined by performing single-point energy calculations and the larger Def2-TZVPP basis set to describe all atoms.^[29] This basis set is designated as BS2. Such single-point calculations employed the same density functional (PBE0) and included the effects of the solvent (toluene) by means of the SMD approach.^[30] In addition, dispersion corrections (D3BJ_{corr}) were also computed on the optimized structures using Grimme's D3 approach with Becke-Johnson damping.^[31] Thus, the Gibbs free energies shown in the manuscript were obtained by adding the previously computed ($E \rightarrow G$)_{corr} and D3BJ_{corr} terms to the PBE0/BS2(SMD) energies. Wiberg bond indices were obtained from the NBO module (Version 3.1) implemented in Gaussian16. The Multiwfn package (version 3.3.9)^[32] was employed to carry out the QTAIM analysis.

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Entry for the Table of Contents

The thermally induced isomerization of **2** into **3** involves the formal migration of a C₃ fragment between the hydrocarbyl ligands and across the plane formed by the three Ru centers. By using computational methods, herein we answer to the main mechanistic questions about this complex transformation that implies the cleavage and formation of Ru–Ru, Ru–C, Ru–H, C–C and C–H bonds.